

The effect of ion pair dynamics on unsaturable absorption in holmium doped fibers

Jan Pokorný^{a,b}, Michal Kamrádek^a, and Pavel Peterka^a

^aInstitute of Photonics and Electronics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Chaberská 1014/57, 182 00 Prague, Czechia

^bFaculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Břehová 7, 115 19 Prague, Czechia

ABSTRACT

We simulate the effect of pair induced quenching in a holmium doped fiber using two numerical models and compare their predictions to measured characteristics. The first model assumes instantaneous decay of doubly excited ion pairs, while the second considers an excited pair lifetime of 438 ns. We show the effect of this difference on the measurement of ion pair content.

Keywords: Fiber laser, holmium

1. INTRODUCTION

Holmium-doped fiber lasers are ideal candidates for highly efficient emitters for the atmospheric transmission window around 2.1 μm . Silica, the material of choice for optical fibers, suffers from low ion solubility, which leads to formation of ion clusters. Some energy transfer processes can be highly promoted in ion clusters, which, in case of holmium, leads to reduced laser efficiency.

Efforts to mitigate ion clustering have borne fruit in recent years with the advancement of fiber preparation techniques. In this case, it was found that increasing the aluminum oxide to holmium doping ratio to 50:1 enhances laser efficiency to 80 % and above in most cases, with little to no influence of the total holmium doping concentration.¹ Aluminum oxide is known to allow the holmium ions to dissolve and form a favorable environment enhancing spectroscopic properties, while also prolonging fluorescent lifetimes.

The ratio of clustered ions should also be much lower. The ratio is usually determined from a consequential effect of pair induced quenching, that being unsaturable absorption.² It was recently found, however, that such an approach is not suitable for holmium-doped fibers due to the relatively long lifetimes of doubly excited (both ions excited) ion pairs, which is of the order of 500 ns. This causes the unsaturable absorption to actually saturate, if probed with high enough pump power.³

This behavior can be modeled numerically by including more energy states an ion pair can occupy instead of only two as is common. The two-level model assumes instantaneous relaxation of doubly excited ions, which is not suitable for the reasons stated above. We numerically model the effect of pair induced quenching in a highly-holmium-doped silica fiber comparing models with instantaneous and measured lifetimes of doubly excited pairs. We compare the models to measurements.

2. MEASUREMENT OF UNSATURABLE ABSORPTION

We measured unsaturable absorption by amplifying a 1950 nm seed thulium doped fiber laser by a two stage amplifier, which we used to probe the power dependent absorption of a holmium doped fiber sample. The setup provided power ranging -30 dBm to 38 dBm, which allowed us to probe both the small signal and saturated regimes by adjusting the pump power in both stages of the amplifier.

The fiber sample (NP1558) was of our own make, having a high holmium doping concentration of 4687 mol ppm and a low aluminum oxide to holmium doping ratio of 8.6:1. The fiber performed relatively poorly in laser resonators, only achieving 41.8 % slope efficiency.⁴ We assume that pair induced quenching is the main contributor to poor efficiency and as such expect a relatively high ratio of clustered ions. The input and transmitted power

was measured using Thorlabs S148C for powers below 24 dBm and Thorlabs 405C-L for powers above 14 dBm, with overlap of the measured powers. A bandpass filter was used to filter out amplified spontaneous emission at wavelengths exceeding 1996 nm. Three lengths of fiber were measured (121 mm, 70 mm, 34 mm) and the transmission values in the small signal and saturated regimes were fitted using a linear fit, as shown in Figure 1a. The slope of the fit was then used to determine the value of small signal and saturated absorption.² The ratio of ions in clusters of two $2k$ was then determined according to

$$2k = \frac{\alpha_{sa}}{\alpha_{ss}} \cdot \frac{2\sigma_a + \sigma_e}{\sigma_a}, \quad (1)$$

where α_{ss} and α_{sa} are the small signal and saturated absorption respectively, and σ_a and σ_e are the Ho absorption and emission cross sections at 1950 nm. The cross section values used are: $\sigma_a = 4.0 \times 10^{-25} m^2$ and $\sigma_e = 4.12 \times 10^{-25} m^2$, which are close to values we observed in our fiber preforms and also reported in literature for similar materials.⁵ We determined the pair content of the fiber sample to $2k = 21.2 \%$.

Figure 1. a) Measured values of small signal and saturated transmission and their slopes with respect to fiber length. b) Measured and simulated values of transmission with respect to input power. Dashed: instantaneous decay model, Solid: accurate decay model

3. MODEL COMPARISON

We implemented two models of holmium fiber lasers: one assuming instantaneous decay of doubly excited ion pairs from Ref. 6 and an accurate decay model assuming the doubly excited pair lifetime of 438 ns from Ref. 3. The implementation of other effects, such as homogeneous upconversion is identical to highlight the difference caused by the treatment of ion pairs.

We present the simulated values of transmission in Figure 1b, for which we used the $2k$ value determined experimentally. The curves produced by both models initially follow the same trajectory, but start to diverge almost exactly where the usual plateau of unsaturable absorption would be expected. Such behavior is consistent with Ref. 3, where an explanation is also provided.

The relatively long doubly excited pair lifetime leads to a high population of doubly excited ions reducing the effect of unsaturable absorption. The measured values, while on the edge of the capability of the measurement setup, seem to follow the solid simulated transmission curve produced by the accurate decay model in Figure 1b. The plateau from which the unsaturable absorption could be accurately determined is not present, which reduces the accuracy of this measurement as its value can only be determined approximately from a narrow range of values.

We also used the two models to calculate the slope efficiency (SE) and threshold power (TH) of a core-pumped CW laser built using the fiber. We obtained values 50.95 % SE and 509 mW TH using the instantaneous decay

model and 53.3 % SE ad 518 mW TH using the accurate decay model. The experimentally determined values were 41.8 % SE and 561 mW TH.⁴ As such the model overestimates the SE and underestimates the TH, but it is difficult to determine the exact cause of the disagreement. For example by using a value of $2k = 27$ % the performance decreases to 41.8 % and 44.3 % SE, and 572 mW and 580 mW TH for the instantaneous and accurate decay models respectively, which provides very good agreement with the laser experiment, but does not agree well with the unsaturable absorption measurement.

As was stated in Ref. 6, there is a variety of spectroscopic values published for the 5I_5 and 5I_6 levels of Ho, and it seems a more thorough determination of these parameters would be beneficial for future models.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We measured and simulated the effect of pair induced quenching in a holmium doped fiber with high doping, comparing two numerical models to the measured characteristics. We found that the computed curves diverge at an important point for the determination of the paired ion content in the fiber, leading to reduced accuracy of the measurement.

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